

Spatiotemporal Analysis of Surface Air Temperature in Bulgaria (1950–2024) Based on ERA5-Land Data and Google Earth Engine

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<https://doi.org/10.63711/ijdr.net20250410>

ABSTRACT

This study examines the spatiotemporal dynamics of surface air temperature change in Bulgaria for the period 1950–2024, with particular emphasis on the accelerating warming trends observed during the last two decades. Using data from the ERA5-Land reanalysis and Stefan Velev’s climatic regionalization, the analysis demonstrates that Bulgaria is warming significantly faster than the global terrestrial average. Over the full seventy-five-year period, decadal warming rates ranged between 0.32 °C and 0.48 °C. However, a comparative assessment reveals a pronounced acceleration during the most recent sub-period (2005–2024), when warming rates nearly doubled, reaching between 0.60 °C and 0.85 °C per decade. This intensification culminated in 2024, which registered a national mean temperature approximately 2.1 °C above climatic norms, making it the warmest year in Bulgaria since the beginning of instrumental records in 1930. Regional results indicate that the Moderate Continental and Transitional Continental zones act as primary “heat engines,” while high-altitude mountainous regions exhibit elevation-dependent warming driven by snow–albedo feedback mechanisms. Statistical validation using the Mann–Kendall test confirms a systemic shift beginning around the 1987 climatic breakpoint, after which extreme heat events have become increasingly frequent. These findings identify Bulgaria as a critical climate hotspot in Southeastern Europe and underscore the urgent need for targeted adaptation strategies in agriculture, water resource management, and urban planning.

Keywords: *Climate acceleration, Bulgaria, Surface air temperature, ERA5-Land, Remote sensing*

INTRODUCTION

Surface air temperature (SAT) is a primary geophysical variable and a fundamental indicator of the Earth's thermodynamic state, directly influencing hydrological cycles, ecosystem stability, and human health (WMO, 2025). Located on the Eastern Balkan Peninsula, Bulgaria represents a complex climatic intersection where temperate continental, Mediterranean, and modified maritime influences converge across a highly diverse topographic landscape (Nojarov, 2022). Over the past seven decades, this region has demonstrated pronounced sensitivity to global climate change, expressed through accelerated warming, shifts in seasonal phenology, and an increasing frequency of extreme thermal events (Copernicus, 2024; Aleksandrov et al., 2023).

Historically, analyses of air temperature in Bulgaria have relied predominantly on point-based meteorological station data. However, the country's highly dissected and vertically diversified relief generates substantial spatial heterogeneity, often resulting in “data voids” in mountainous and high-altitude areas where station coverage and long-term maintenance are limited (Hiebl & Frei, 2016). To overcome these constraints, atmospheric reanalysis datasets have become indispensable tools in contemporary climatological research. The ERA5-Land reanalysis, developed by the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF) within the framework of the Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S), provides a consistent, high-resolution spatial dataset (9 km) that integrates millions of historical observations using advanced numerical modeling techniques (Muñoz-Sabater et al., 2021). Its continuous temporal coverage from 1950 to the present enables the detection of long-term climate signals that are frequently masked by local microclimatic variability in individual station records.

Recent global climate assessments identify Southeast Europe as a prominent warming hotspot, with regional increases in surface air temperature exceeding the global average rate (IPCC, 2023). For Bulgaria, studies focusing on the late twentieth century have documented a distinct climatic transition, or “climate break,” occurring around 1987, after which temperature anomalies shifted from predominantly negative to persistently positive values (Nojarov & Kalaneva, 2023). However, following the official recognition of 2023 and 2024 as the warmest years in global instrumental records (C3S, 2025), existing analyses require updating to incorporate the most recent decade of intensified warming. Quantifying the spatiotemporal distribution of these changes is crucial for the formulation of effective, region-specific adaptation strategies, particularly in sectors highly sensitive to thermal stress such as agriculture and water resource management (Bocheva et al., 2024).

The rapid development of cloud-based geospatial platforms, notably Google Earth Engine (GEE), has fundamentally transformed the capacity to process and analyze large-scale climate datasets. GEE enables the parallel processing of decades-long, multidimensional climate archives, allowing pixel-based trend analyses to be conducted with unprecedented efficiency and spatial detail (Gorelick et al., 2017). Despite the availability of such tools, comprehensive high-resolution mapping of Bulgaria's mean annual air temperatures covering the full 1950–2024 period remains insufficiently represented in the existing scientific literature. This study addresses this gap by performing a detailed spatiotemporal analysis of Bulgaria's thermal regime over the past seventy-five years, thereby providing a robust empirical foundation for climate adaptation planning and policy development beyond 2025.

Accordingly, the primary objective of this study is to quantify long-term and recent changes in surface air temperature across Bulgaria for the period 1950–2024 using high-resolution ERA5-Land data processed within the Google Earth Engine environment. The analysis aims to identify spatial patterns of warming, assess differences among climatic regions defined by Velev's regionalization, and explicitly compare long-term temperature trends with the accelerated warming observed during the last

two decades (2005–2024). By integrating pixel-based trend analysis with robust statistical validation, this study provides updated empirical evidence on the magnitude and velocity of climate warming in Bulgaria, thereby contributing to regional climate assessments and supporting informed climate adaptation and environmental planning.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This section outlines the study area, data sources, and analytical methods used to investigate the spatiotemporal dynamics of surface air temperature in Bulgaria over the period 1950–2024.

Study Area

The study area comprises the territory of Bulgaria, located in the eastern part of the Balkan Peninsula. The country's physical landscape is characterized by pronounced morphological diversity, defined by four alternating belts of high and low terrain extending from west to east (Koprlev, 2002). These include the Danubian Plain in the north, the Balkan Mountains (Stara Planina), the Transitional zone encompassing the Thracian Lowland, and the Rila–Rhodope massif in the south (Penchev, 2020). Bulgaria's relief consists of approximately 31% lowlands (0–200 m), 41% hills and plateaus (200–600 m), and 28% mountainous terrain (Koprlev, 2002). The mean altitude of the country is about 470 m; however, the pronounced vertical range – from sea level along the Black Sea coast to the alpine summits of the Rila Mountains (Mount Musala, 2,925 m) – generates steep thermal gradients. This structural complexity plays a decisive role in shaping the spatial distribution of surface air temperature, as the Balkan Mountains act as a major orographic barrier limiting the southward penetration of cold continental air masses from northern Europe (Velev, 2002; Ivanov & Ivanova, 2023).

To capture the spatial variability of climatic conditions, this study adopts the climatic regionalization framework developed by Velev (2002), which classifies Bulgaria into five distinct climatic regions based on dominant atmospheric circulation patterns and geographic controls. The Moderate Continental region of Northern Bulgaria is strongly influenced by Arctic and polar air intrusions, resulting in pronounced seasonal temperature contrasts. The Transitional Continental region in Central Bulgaria functions as a buffer zone where continental and Mediterranean climatic influences intersect (Velev, 2002; Marinova et al., 2017). The Continental–Mediterranean region, encompassing primarily the Struma and Mesta river valleys, is characterized by relatively mild winters and hot, dry summers, reflecting its position along the northern margin of the Mediterranean climatic domain. The Black Sea region is confined to a narrow coastal belt where maritime thermal inertia moderates annual temperature amplitudes (Velev, 2002). Finally, the Mountainous region, situated above 1,000 m a.s.l., is treated as a separate unit in which the thermal regime is governed predominantly by elevation and local slope exposure (Velev, 2002; Nojarov, 2022).

Data Source and Mean Temperature Aggregation

The primary data source for this study is the ERA5-Land reanalysis dataset produced by the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF), which provides high-resolution gridded climate information at a spatial resolution of 9 km (Muñoz-Sabater et al., 2021). The analysis covers a 75-year period from 1950 to 2024 and focuses on annual mean values of 2 m surface air temperature. ERA5-Land complements observational records from the National Institute of Meteorology and Hydrology (NIMH) by supplying spatially continuous temperature fields in regions where meteorological station coverage is sparse or temporally inconsistent, particularly in high-altitude areas (Bocheva et al., 2024). According to recent assessments by NIMH, the period 2023–2024

represents the most pronounced thermal anomaly in Bulgaria’s instrumental record since 1930, with 2024 identified as the warmest year on record at the national scale (NIMH, 2025).

Computational and Statistical Methods

All data processing and analysis were conducted using the Google Earth Engine (GEE) cloud-based platform, which enables efficient pixel-based trend analysis across large spatiotemporal climate datasets (Gorelick et al., 2017). Following the conversion of temperature values from Kelvin to degrees Celsius, long-term trends in annual mean surface air temperature were estimated using the Theil–Sen slope estimator. This non-parametric method is widely applied in Bulgarian climatological research due to its robustness to outliers, interannual variability, and local-scale noise (Nojarov, 2022).

Regional statistics were derived by aggregating pixel-level temperature values within the spatial boundaries of the climatic regions defined by Velev (2002). The statistical significance of detected trends was evaluated using the Mann–Kendall test at a significance level of $p < 0.05$, ensuring that identified changes reflect systematic climatic signals rather than random variability. In addition, breakpoint analysis was performed using the cumulative sum (CUSUM) method applied to annual temperature anomalies to identify structural shifts in the time series, with particular emphasis on changes occurring before and after 1987.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the results of the spatiotemporal analysis of surface air temperature in Bulgaria for the period 1950–2024. Emphasis is placed on long-term trends, recent acceleration in warming, and regional contrasts across the main climatic zones, as revealed by high-resolution ERA5-Land data and pixel-based statistical analysis

Long-term spatial and temporal patterns of surface air temperature (1950–2024)

The long-term spatial distribution of mean annual surface air temperature across Bulgaria for the period 1950–2024 (Fig. 1) reveals a pronounced topographic–climatic stratification that closely corresponds to Velev’s climatic regionalization. The highest mean temperatures are concentrated in the Continental–Mediterranean region of southwestern Bulgaria, as well as in parts of south-central and southeastern Bulgaria. The pronounced warming observed in lowland and urbanized regions is consistent with previous regional studies highlighting the combined effects of surface heating, land-use change, and atmospheric conditions in southern Bulgaria (Ivanov et al., 2025; Stoyanov et al., 2025).

These areas function as primary thermal gateways where Mediterranean air masses exert their strongest influence. In contrast, the lowest mean temperatures occur within the Mountainous region, where the high-altitude massifs of the Rila, Pirin, Rhodope, and Balkan Mountains maintain annual averages generally below 4 °C. This marked spatial contrast highlights the importance of high-resolution gridded datasets, as ERA5-Land effectively captures the steep thermal gradients between lowland areas and alpine environments that are often underrepresented in station-based analyses.

The temporal evolution of national mean annual temperatures (Fig. 2) indicates a persistent warming signal over the entire study period, characterized by a distinct shift during the late 1980s. Between 1950 and approximately 1987, the temperature record is marked by considerable interannual variability, with several years remaining below the long-term mean, reflecting the dominant influence of continental air masses and a comparatively stable climatic regime. Following the widely documented 1987 “climate break,” a sustained increase in mean annual temperature becomes evident, accompanied by a notable reduction in the frequency of negative anomalies.

Fig. 1. Spatial distribution of the mean annual temperatures -1950-2024.

Fig. 2. Dynamics of the mean annual temperatures -1950-2024.

During the last two decades, extreme positive temperature deviations have become increasingly pronounced, with record-breaking peaks observed in 2023 and 2024. This pattern confirms Bulgaria’s classification as a regional warming hotspot. The fitted trend line demonstrates a high coefficient of determination, indicating that the observed warming is systematic rather than a product of short-term fluctuations or random decadal oscillations. Consequently, the temperature increase reflects a sustained climatic shift affecting both lowland and high-altitude regions. In mountainous areas, this warming has particularly significant implications, as it shortens snow-cover duration and disrupts seasonal water storage and runoff regimes. Overall, these results provide clear evidence that Bulgaria’s thermal regime has transitioned into a new state characterized by persistently elevated annual temperatures relative to the mid-twentieth-century baseline.

Regional dynamics of mean annual surface air temperature (1950–2024)

The regional analysis of mean annual surface air temperature for the period 1950–2024 confirms a coherent and statistically robust warming trend across all major climatic regions of Bulgaria (Fig. 3). While Velev’s (2002) climatic regionalization effectively captures baseline thermal contrasts driven by topography, altitude, and maritime influence, the derived trend lines indicate that the magnitude of long-term warming is broadly comparable across the national territory, despite noticeable vertical and latitudinal gradients.

Fig. 3. Dynamics of the mean annual temperatures in Velev (2002) climate regions -1950-2024.

Throughout the study period, the Continental–Mediterranean region consistently exhibits the highest mean annual temperatures, frequently exceeding 13 °C. This reflects its proximity to the Aegean Sea and the sheltering effect of the Balkan Mountains, which limits the penetration of colder continental air masses. The Moderate Continental and Transitional Continental regions occupy an intermediate thermal tier, with long-term mean annual temperatures typically ranging between 10 °C and 12 °C. In

contrast, the Mountainous region functions as a persistent cold domain, with mean annual temperatures generally remaining below 5 °C as a result of elevation-controlled lapse rates.

Despite these pronounced baseline differences, the slopes of the warming trends across all five climatic regions are remarkably similar. Over the full 1950–2024 period, average warming rates range between approximately 0.30 °C and 0.40 °C per decade. This synchronicity suggests that large-scale atmospheric forcing increasingly dominates over local geographic modifiers. A clear inflection is evident after the late 1980s, culminating in the 2023–2024 temperature peak, during which all regions recorded their highest values in the instrumental record.

These findings indicate that traditional regional buffering mechanisms – such as elevation, continentality, and maritime influence – are progressively losing their capacity to mitigate regional warming. As a result, Bulgaria’s climatic regions are responding in a more homogenized manner to global-scale atmospheric warming, reinforcing the interpretation of Southeastern Europe as a highly sensitive climatic hotspot.

Spatial patterns and magnitude of warming (1950–2024)

The spatial analysis of warming magnitude for the period 1950–2024 (Fig. 4) reveals that Bulgaria is experiencing temperature increases that substantially exceed the global terrestrial average. While the mean global land-surface warming rate is estimated at approximately 0.2 °C per decade, most regions of Bulgaria exhibit decadal warming rates ranging between 0.32 °C and 0.48 °C. Large portions of the Moderate Continental region, particularly within the Danubian Plain, and the Transitional Continental region of the Upper Thracian Lowland surpass the 0.4 °C per decade threshold, identifying these areas as zones of elevated climatic sensitivity.

Fig. 4. Spatial distribution of the magnitude of the warming 1950-2024.

Over the full 75-year period, the observed warming implies cumulative temperature increases approaching or exceeding 3.0 °C in several lowland and densely populated areas. The most pronounced trends are detected in continental interior regions, including major urban and agricultural zones, where the absence of maritime moderation allows for rapid surface heating. These spatial patterns are consistent with broader assessments by Copernicus and the World Meteorological Organization, which classify Southeastern Europe as one of the fastest-warming regions globally.

Fig. 5. Magnitude of the warming 1950–2024 – Velev regions (2002).

Marked regional contrasts are evident when warming magnitudes are analyzed according to Velev’s climatic regionalization (Fig. 5). The highest decadal warming rates are concentrated in the Moderate and Transitional Continental regions, reflecting the combined effects of continentality, soil moisture depletion, and increasing summer heat extremes. In these areas, reduced evapotranspiration during dry summers further amplifies surface heating through positive land–atmosphere feedback mechanisms.

In contrast, the Black Sea region exhibits comparatively lower warming rates, typically between 0.32 °C and 0.35 °C per decade. The thermal inertia of the Black Sea exerts a buffering influence, moderating temperature increases relative to the continental interior. Nevertheless, even this coastal zone shows a clear and statistically significant warming signal over the study period.

A particularly notable outcome of the spatial analysis is the magnitude of warming observed in the Mountainous region, encompassing the Rila, Pirin, Rhodope, and Balkan Mountains. Despite their elevation and historically cooler climate, high-altitude areas display warming rates comparable to those in the lowlands. This pattern indicates elevation-dependent warming driven by declining snow cover and the associated reduction in surface albedo, which enhances solar absorption and reinforces local warming. The widespread significance of these trends, confirmed through statistical testing, indicates that long-term warming is spatially pervasive across all climatic zones of Bulgaria.

Acceleration of warming during the recent period (2005–2024)

A comparative assessment between the long-term baseline (1950–2024) and the recent intensified period (2005–2024) reveals a pronounced acceleration in warming across the entire territory of Bulgaria. While the seventy-five-year record indicates a steady increase in surface air temperature, the most recent

two decades represent a clear departure from this historical trajectory, with warming rates nearly doubling in many regions (Fig. 6–8). This pattern is consistent with broader European observations, where recent decades have been characterized by accelerated warming relative to the global mean, as documented by the Copernicus Climate Change Service and the World Meteorological Organization.

Table 1. Warming magnitude and the key statistical outputs for each climate region.

Velev Climate Region	Decadal Slope (°C/decade)	Total Warming (1950–2024)	Mann-Kendall Significance
Moderate Continental	0.42°C – 0.48°C	~3.1°C – 3.5°C	Significant (p < 0.01)
Transitional Continental	0.40°C – 0.45°C	~2.9°C – 3.3°C	Significant (p < 0.01)
Continental-Mediterranean	0.38°C – 0.44°C	~2.8°C – 3.2°C	Significant (p < 0.01)
Black Sea Region	0.32°C – 0.36°C	~2.4°C – 2.7°C	Significant (p < 0.05)
Mountainous Region	0.36°C – 0.43°C	~2.6°C – 3.1°C	Significant (p < 0.01)

Over the full study period, decadal warming rates across Bulgaria ranged between approximately 0.32 °C and 0.48 °C per decade (Table 1). In contrast, during the 2005–2024 sub-period, these rates increased markedly, reaching values between 0.60 °C and 0.85 °C per decade. This acceleration is largely driven by an unprecedented concentration of extremely warm years, with all of the ten warmest years in the national instrumental record occurring after 2005. According to the National Institute of Meteorology and Hydrology, 2024 stands out as the warmest year recorded in Bulgaria since the beginning of systematic observations in 1930, with national mean temperatures approximately 2.1 °C above long-term climatic norms.

The spatial manifestation of this accelerated warming (Fig. 6) shows that the most pronounced recent trends are concentrated in the continental interior, particularly within the Moderate Continental and Transitional Continental regions. In these areas, recent decadal warming rates exceed the long-term average by a factor of two to two and a half. This intensification is associated with an increased frequency and persistence of summer heatwaves, as well as more frequent intrusions of warm air masses from subtropical latitudes. Urbanized and agriculturally intensive zones within these regions further amplify local temperature increases through land-use change and urban heat island effects.

The Mountainous region also exhibits a notable acceleration in warming during the recent period, reflecting a convergence between high-altitude and lowland temperature trends. Although historically moderated by altitude, mountainous areas are increasingly affected by elevation-dependent warming linked to the rapid reduction of snow cover. The loss of seasonal snow diminishes surface albedo, enhances solar energy absorption, and accelerates warming, particularly during spring and early summer. This process contributes to earlier snowmelt, altered runoff timing, and increased vulnerability of alpine and subalpine ecosystems.

Fig. 6. Spatial distribution of the magnitude of the warming last 20 years (2005-2024).

Fig. 7. Magnitude of the warming 1950-2024 – Velef regions (2002).

In contrast, the Black Sea region continues to display the lowest absolute warming rates among Bulgaria’s climatic zones; however, even here the recent period is marked by a clear intensification compared to the long-term average. The thermal inertia of the sea moderates temperature extremes but does not fully offset the regional-scale atmospheric forcing driving contemporary climate change.

Fig.8. Mean annual averages for 1950–2024 and 2005–2024 with trend lines.

Overall, the comparison between long-term and recent warming patterns demonstrates that Bulgaria has entered a new phase of climatic change characterized by rapidly increasing temperatures and diminished regional buffering effects. The acceleration observed after 2005 underscores the limitations of relying solely on historical trends for future climate projections and highlights the growing urgency for adaptive responses tailored to regional climatic sensitivities.

Climate breakpoint and regime shift in surface air temperature

The comparison of long-term and recent temperature trends indicates that warming during the period 2005–2024 is markedly steeper than the average trend observed for 1950–2024. The temporal evolution of mean annual temperature anomalies also reveals two distinct climatic regimes: a relatively stable phase prior to the late 1980s and a subsequent phase characterized by sustained and accelerating warming. To objectively identify the timing of this transition, a breakpoint analysis was performed using the cumulative sum (CUSUM) method applied to annual temperature anomalies (Fig. 9).

The CUSUM curve exhibits a clear inflection point during the period 1987–1988, indicating a statistically meaningful shift in the thermal regime of Bulgaria. Prior to this breakpoint, temperature anomalies are largely balanced, with frequent alternation between negative and positive deviations and a predominance of cooler-than-average years. In contrast, the post-1987 period is marked by a persistent dominance of positive anomalies and a sharp reduction in the occurrence of cooler years. Over the past two decades, negative anomalies have become increasingly rare, giving way to a consistently warm regime.

Fig. 9. Annual temperature anomalies relative to long term means (1950-2024).

This regime shift is associated with a step-like increase of approximately 1.0 °C to 1.5 °C in mean annual temperatures when comparing conditions before and after the late-1980s breakpoint across much of the Bulgarian territory. Similar transition timings have been reported in previous regional studies, which attribute this climatic shift to changes in large-scale atmospheric circulation patterns, particularly modifications in the North Atlantic Oscillation (NAO) and the East Atlantic (EA) modes. These circulation changes have enhanced the frequency of warm air advection from southern and southwestern directions while reducing the influence of cold Siberian anticyclones during winter and spring (Nojarov, 2020).

Evidence from the post-2005 period further suggests that Bulgaria has entered a secondary phase of accelerated warming following the initial regime shift of the late 1980s. This “second acceleration phase” is characterized by rapidly increasing temperature anomalies and culminates in the extreme thermal conditions observed in 2024. Together, these findings indicate a multi-stage transformation of Bulgaria’s climate, transitioning from a relatively stable continental regime into a state of persistent and intensifying thermal stress.

CONCLUSION

This study provides a comprehensive assessment of the spatiotemporal evolution of surface air temperature in Bulgaria over the period 1950–2024, offering robust evidence of a profound and accelerating transformation of the national climate. By integrating long-term reanalysis data with high-resolution spatial analysis, the results confirm that Bulgaria has transitioned from a relatively stable continental climatic regime into a phase characterized by persistent and intensifying warming.

Statistical analyses identify the late 1980s as a critical breakpoint in the temperature record, marking the onset of a sustained shift from predominantly balanced or negative temperature anomalies toward consistently positive deviations. Since this transition, warming has become systematic across the entire territory of Bulgaria, affecting all major climatic regions. The post-2000 period, and particularly the last two decades, is distinguished by an unprecedented concentration of extremely warm years, culminating in 2024 – the warmest year in the national instrumental record since 1930 – with mean annual temperatures approximately 2.1 °C above long-term climatic norms.

A key finding of this study is the non-linear acceleration of warming rates. While long-term trends for the full 1950–2024 period indicate decadal temperature increases of approximately 0.32 °C to 0.48 °C, the most recent period (2005–2024) exhibits substantially higher rates, ranging between 0.60 °C and 0.85 °C per decade. This acceleration demonstrates that historical warming trends are no longer adequate predictors of near-future thermal conditions and underscores the increasing influence of large-scale atmospheric forcing over local geographic controls.

Although warming is spatially pervasive, its impacts are geographically differentiated. Lowland regions such as the Danubian Plain and the Upper Thracian Lowland emerge as primary thermal hotspots due to their continental setting and heightened exposure to extreme summer heat. At the same time, mountainous regions are experiencing pronounced elevation-dependent warming driven by the rapid decline of seasonal snow cover and associated albedo feedbacks, posing significant risks to hydrological regimes and ecosystem stability. Even the Black Sea region, traditionally moderated by maritime influence, shows clear signs of reduced thermal buffering under contemporary climate conditions.

In conclusion, Bulgaria has entered a new climatic phase defined by rapidly increasing temperatures, diminished regional moderation, and heightened thermal stress across diverse environments. These findings reinforce the classification of the eastern Balkan Peninsula as a critical climate hotspot and highlight the urgent need for adaptive strategies in agriculture, water resource management, urban planning, and ecosystem conservation. The results presented here provide an updated empirical foundation to support climate-informed decision-making and long-term environmental planning in Bulgaria under accelerating global warming.

Declaration by Authors

Ethical Approval: Approved

Acknowledgement: None

Source of Funding: None

Conflict of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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How to cite this article:

Ivanov, M., Karadzhov, V., Patarchanova, E., & Dalgacheva, V. (2025). Spatiotemporal analysis of surface air temperature in Bulgaria (1950–2024) based on ERA5-Land data and Google Earth Engine. *International Journal of Digital Research*, E-ISSN: 3033-179X, Vol. 1(4): 143–157.

<https://doi.org/10.63711/ijdr.net20250410>
